

ICT Services for Electro-Mobility

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Abstract

The evolution of mobility in a sustainable perspective requires specific attention to the end-users roles and the changing needs of the cities and policies. This work shows how ICT (Information and Communications Technology) services can allow the transition towards smart and sustainable mobility. Within the European project H2020 ELVITEN (GA nr. 769926), a proper set of ICT services are described, including: the brokering and the booking service for vehicles and charging stations, the ICT platform for monitoring the fleet of electric vehicles, the serious game app and a smart app for incentives. These services are suitable and indispensable to incentivize and encourage users towards a new mobility that is electric and sustainable.

Keywords:

Electro-mobility, ICT services, Smart mobility

1. Introduction

Mobility in smart cities is an interesting topic on ever-increasing evolution. Cities are becoming more and more populous, and a smart mobility planning within the context of smart cities is a tacking challenge. Recent studies show that, in European countries, the most frequent trip is made by car: car usage represents about 60% of total transport modes used [1] and causes several problems both to drivers and citizens. The extensive use of cars makes the existing transport systems not efficient, resulting in negative effects such as urban traffic congestion, parking shortages, air pollution (e.g., increase in particulate matter, nitrogen oxides), and noise pollution. Some of the aforementioned issues are very dangerous for human health [2] and produce economic and social losses [3]. The transport sector is one of the main responsible for the production of greenhouse gases emissions that are causing climate change. All these factors negatively affect the quality of life and health of urban citizens.

In this context, the United Nations Agenda 2030 stands out as a plan of action for people to preserve the planet and foster prosperity. The Agenda is based on seventeen Sustainable Development Goals with definite targets and indicators. Several Sustainable Development Goals are linked to the improvement of the quality of life in urban areas [4]. On the other hand, the Roadmap 2050, implemented by the

European Commission with the objective of decarbonization (80% decrease in CO₂ emission since 1990), aims to ban the circulation of conventional internal combustion engine cars in cities by 2050 and “the use of smaller, lighter and more specialized road passenger vehicles”. The Roadmap actions encourage clean urban mobility and commuting.

Electric L-category Vehicles (EL-Vs) are a useful alternative to fulfil both citizens’ and commuters’ needs within urban areas [5]. EL-Vs are small vehicles with 2, 3 or 4 wheels, such as mopeds, motorbikes, quads, tricycles and quadricycles. The main advantages of EL-Vs are their small size, light weight, agility, low operating and maintenance costs, low emissions and noise, energy saving, and high suitability for the daily needs of the average citizen. In recent years, new EL-Vs models and related innovative solutions are being implemented, making them increasingly attractive to a wider audience; as a result, the potential market is growing strongly [6]. Currently, the limiting factors to the diffusion of EL-Vs are the users’ low awareness about the performance and functionalities and, in part, the limited direct experience in using EL-Vs.

Modern Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) are allowing significant improvement in the mobility sector, especially for electromobility [7]. The ICT tools allow incentivizing and facilitating the use of EL-Vs by providing services such as booking and brokering of EL-Vs, charging stations, parking spots, as well as payments and vehicle monitoring. It must be remarked that EL-Vs usage schemes are expected to provide useful ICT tools to the users.

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This paper describes some innovative ICT tools which have been devised on the basis of a first analysis of the existing services for EL-Vs, together with ICT tools that can be implemented to improve EL-Vs usage. Therefore, the novelty of this paper resides in the definition of ICT services necessary to allow a high usage of EL-Vs in the demonstration sites. The paper is organized as follows. Section 2 summarizes the ICT services in the smart cities’ context. Section 3 reports the application of the proposed ICT services within the ELVITEN EU project. Finally, Section 4 reports the conclusions.

2. ICT services in the smart city context

Cities are becoming more and more populous and a smart mobility planning within the context of smart cities is a tacking challenge [8], [9], [10]. The improvement of the cities sustainability and the urban quality of life are the major objectives of the researchers for the future mobility system [11], [12].

The smart city definition has several meanings. A city can be smart:

- on the “*environmental aspect*”, characterized by low CO₂ emission, use of renewable energy sources and low energy consumptions;
- on the “*living aspect*”, characterized by co-working system and several cultural initiatives;
- on the “*governance aspect*”, when the citizens are involved on all the pulic topics;
- on the “*economy*”, with a strictly cooperation among public and private actors and great synergy

among them;

- for the “*people*”, where a network is created among them with the sharing of data, information and communication among them;
- on the “*mobility*” aspect, where several high technologies can be used to improve the urban mobility and allow the reduction of environmental impact. This new vision of mobility is characterized to improve the urban traffic and inhabitant mobility on the basis on sustainability, innovation and safe transport.

Figure 1 – Smart City definition

Modern ICT solutions allow significant improvement in the mobility sector, especially for electro-mobility and sharing systems.

The ICT tools allow to incentivize and facilitate the use of Electric Vehicles (EV) by providing services such as booking and brokering, charging station, parking spots, as well as payments and vehicle monitoring.

3. ELVITEN project and ICT services for electro-mobility sector

ELVITEN is a Research and Innovation Action (RIA) funded by the European Union’s Horizon2020 Programme under Grant Agreement No. 769926. It started in November 2017 and it will finish in October 2020.

The ELVITEN project focuses on mobility analysis and implementation of Electric L-category Vehicles (ELVs) in six European Cities: Genoa, Rome, Bari, Malaga, Berlin and Trikala.

ELVITEN aims to holistically tackle all issues impeding the wide market deployment of EL-Vs. The main aim of ELVITEN project is to propose replicable usage schemes to boost ownership or sharing of all categories of EL-Vs by both systematic and occasional urban travellers and light delivery companies. One-year long demonstrations with the equipped EL-Vs of all will allow the collection of a big data bank of trip data and users' experiences and opinions during the trips.

Based on the foreseen EL-Vs usage schemes, the types of EL-Vs, and other facilities (e-hub), the ICT services to be deployed in each city are defined. In particular, by analysing the existing ICT assets available in each city, the ICT functionalities to be adapted and implemented are defined, by identifying interactions between the various service providers.

Existing charge points in the six ELVITEN Demonstration Cities, including private ones, are integrated in a Brokering and Booking service and EL-Vs charging possibilities to enable EL-Vs users to charge independently from charge point operators. In detail, the designed ICT tools are:

- the Brokering and a Booking service for EL-Vs and charge/parking points;
- the EL-Vs fleet monitoring tool;
- the Serious Game;
- the Incentive Management platform.

Figure 2 shows the ICT services developed in the ELVITEN project and Table 1 reports the main goals and features of each service.

Figure 2 – ICT services in ELVITEN

ICT Services	Main goals	Features
Booking and brokering service	Allow ELVITEN users to book resources with a handheld device	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Book vehicles 2. Book charging points 3. Book parking spaces 4. Cancel bookings 5. Fill in questionnaires
EL-V fleet monitoring APP	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Collect trips' data 2. Collect questionnaires 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. User-reported trip start / stop 2. User-reported trip purpose

		<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3. Fill in app-related questionnaires 4. Discover trip score 5. Access historical data (trips and score history)
Serious Game	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Engage users into the project via gaming 2. Collect questionnaires 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Show data regarding the City and Electric Light Vehicles 2. Ask questions to gain points 3. Collect points to reach achievements 4. Reach point of Interest in the city to discover the city 5. Fill in app-related questionnaires
Incentive Smart APP	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Incentivize the use of ELVITEN services 2. Collect questionnaires 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Discover rewarded actions (rules) 2. Browse and claim awards 3. Monitor available and used points 4. Access historical data (rewarded actions and vouchers) 5. Fill in app-related questionnaires

Table 1 – ICT services, main goals and features

The developed ICT services are described in the following subsections.

E-Brokering Service for EL-Vs and charge points

E-Brokering Service includes functionalities for forward, capacity, day-ahead and intraday. The service is connected with local sharing and charging service providers’ systems. E-Brokering Service requires access to an inventory of resources (EL-Vs, charging points and parking spaces) and is capable to manage resource synchronization with third party providers or a centralized data base. E-Brokering Service provides information about availability and requirement of resources per time-slot. This information is used and updated by the E-Booking Service. E-Brokering Service provides an API test web page as well as the E-Booking Service does.

E-Booking Service of e-charging points

E-Booking Service uses data provided by EL-Vs parking stations and charging points to calculate availability of shared vehicles and charging points. It enables the integration of public and private charging points for EL-Vs.

E-Booking Service provides a list of charging points based on proximity, including location data that could be used by a third-party to display them on maps. Both services can “run” locally at ICT infrastructure provided by the city, or remotely on ELVITEN servers. Figure 3 shows the screenshot of the booking app by the ELVITEN users.

Figure 3 – Booking APP

Serious Game

A Serious game app is deployed to give more information to the users about the project, the EL-Vs and the City itself. Framework customizations for the different Cities are foreseen. The mobile application is based on a Java Script edition language.

The basic idea is linked to simple quizzes where user answers similarly to the “trivial pursuit” game. In each city, a series of multiple questions are linked to specific tourist places: based on GPS position, when the user will be close to a monumental street, or church, square etc. the app will be active and user will be able to answer to these questions in the city, as sort of treasure hunt for the city.

The APP is customized for each city. The list of points of interest, with their location and linked questions AND the list of all the questions are contained in external resource files written in XML. When the user selects the city he is, the app downloads the adequate resource files.

The base code is the same as the rules of a game. The app is independent and is available on the google play portal and is available only for Android.

The cities where the game is deployed have created create two files: a) the list of point of interest, b) the list of quizzes. These questions are useful to help EL-Vs users, tourists in particular, to “discover” well known places in the city or maybe some “hidden gems” like places not very famous but worth a visit. Figure 4 shows some screenshots of the serious game app.

Figure 4 – Serious Game app

EL-Vs Fleet monitoring and Digital Coach app

The EL-Vs in all cities to be involved in the demonstrations are equipped with the trip data loggers (black boxes). Owners of private EL-Vs (in Genoa and Berlin) will sign a consent form before their vehicles’ instrumentation.

In addition, EL-Vs fleet monitoring tool and digital coach app is deployed based on their actual proprietary application. The tool is accessible through a web application, does not require local installation and is compatible with any device with internet access. It collects data from the black boxes installed on the EL-Vs, generates an in-depth profiling of usage, routes and driving behaviour of the users of different vehicle types and outputs specific reports for the fleet operators. Furthermore, a mobile application provides feedback to the drivers on their driving behaviour, giving detailed tips with relation to the route on the map and how the trip could have been done better in terms of driving style and vehicle type. Additionally, the app generates motivating suggestions to boost EL-V usage. purposes. In detail, the following figures show the use cases services for fleet management:

Figure 5. Use case of black box vehicle integration

Figure 6. Use case of vehicle usage

Figure 7. Use case of vehicle repairs

Incentive Management System

The incentive management system, developed starting from the EPPI platform [13], is primarily composed by the incentive administration panel, through which operators can define incentives’ rules, and the Incentive Smart App (ISA), a mobile app for the ELVITEN users that is integrated with both the ELVITEN authentication and authorization system and the administration panel. The smart app implements the incentives model to reward citizen’s virtuous behaviour, such as the usage of an EL-V instead of ICE vehicles. Virtuous behaviours result in the collection of eco-points which are exchanged with discount vouchers, for example for the deployed services (parking, charging, rental) and for other services and goods.

The structure of the Smart App was designed in order to be easily customized across the Demonstration Cities.

The functionalities exposed by the ISA are:

- User login via the ELVITEN authentication system;
- Listing of all behaviours currently incentivized by the Municipality of the user’s registration site;
- Listing of all the available rewards for the user’s registration site;
- Checking the current user’s eco-points balance;
- Spending the accumulated eco-points in rewards;
- Questionnaires’ administration.

Figure 8. Incentive smart APP

4. Conclusions

This paper presents the ICT services developed in the electro-mobility sector as means to allow significant improvement in the mobility sector, incentivize and facilitate the use of Electric Vehicles (EV) by providing different services and ensure high flexibility in order to sustain a good and motivating experience for EL-Vs users. The ICT services can allow the transition to smart mobility by improving the urban traffic and inhabitants' mobility on the basis of sustainability, innovation and safe transport. A proper set of ICT tools can motivate and support people to use EL-Vs, making them suitable to substitute conventional internal combustion engine vehicles.

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